

**CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED AND STRATEGIES ADOPTED BY TEACHERS
IN FACE-TO-FACE MODALITY IN RELATION TO PERFORMANCE
OF PUPILS: BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 10

Pages: 1574-1582

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2933

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14712374

Manuscript Accepted: 12-31-2024

Challenges Encountered and Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-To-Face Modality in Relation to Performance of Pupils: Basis for Enhancement

Loradel G. Robles,* Nelson G. Bedaura
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the extent of challenges encountered and the extent of strategies adopted by teachers in the face-to-face modality in relation to the performance of pupils. This quantitative study was conducted among 129 public elementary school teachers for the school year 2022-2023 in the District of La Castellana II. Findings revealed that majority of the respondents were female, married and with more than ten years of teaching experience. The challenges greatly encountered were on educational trends and technology. Individualized instruction was the strategy frequently adopted. Pupils' academic performance showed satisfactory result. This led to conclusion that teachers teach best in face-to-face mode despite the challenges encountered and utilized strategies to create conducive learning environment.

Keywords: *challenges, strategies modality, performance, enhancement*

Introduction

According to Fauzi et al., (2020) noted that among the challenges experienced by teachers during the pandemic were a shortage of opportunities, internet use, implementing and evaluating learning, and working with parents to ensure that the results were legitimate and trustworthy. Rasmitadila et al. (2020) opined that teacher faced problems in distance learning implementation like technical issues, learner's behavior towards online education.

Given the situation, the challenges faced by teachers in the District of La Castellana II, Division of Negros Occidental, highlight the resilience and adaptability required during times of significant change, such as those brought about by education reform and the pandemic. The ability of teachers to adapt various strategies to sustain their work and continue teaching despite these challenges. Ensuring the continuity of basic education and offering quality learning experiences for elementary school learners remains essential. This requires a collaborative effort involving not only teachers but also educational authorities, communities, and other stakeholders. By providing support, resources, and innovative solutions, teachers can navigate these challenges more effectively and ensure that every child receives the education they deserve, regardless of the circumstances.

In addition, educators must be able to adapt and prepare themselves for important and practical ways to impart knowledge. They must adopt innovations, interventions, and methods that will simplify and ease their work. To support student learning, learner differentiation, and learner-centeredness, educators should successfully address the issues they face today. This study is crucial for understanding the challenges teachers encounter and the innovative strategies they employ to persevere in their teaching roles. By recognizing these difficulties and strategies, this can be a better support for teachers in delivering effective instruction and ensuring continued learning opportunities for all learners.

Therefore, this research aimed to determine the extent of challenges encountered by teachers and strategies they adopted in face-to-face modality. This will also determine its relation to the performance of pupils and how these will be the parameter to steer and lead the issues and concerns in the public elementary schools in the district of La Castellana II in the post pandemic.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of challenges encountered and strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality in relation to the performance of pupils in the District of La Castellana II, Division of Negros Occidental. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables?
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. length of service; and
 - 1.3. civil status?
2. What is the extent of challenges encountered by teachers in face-to-face modality in the following areas:
 - 2.1. parental support;
 - 2.2. behavior management;
 - 2.3. communication;
 - 2.4. administrative work;
 - 2.5. learning styles; and
 - 2.6. educational trends and technology?
3. What is the extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality in the following areas:

- 3.1. video-based;
- 3.2. game-based;
- 3.3. collaborative learning approach;
- 3.4. individualized instruction; and
- 3.5. inquiry-based approach?
4. What is the level of performance of pupils?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of challenges encountered and extent of strategies adopted by teachers?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of challenges encountered and level of academic performance of pupils?
7. Is there significant relationship between extent of strategies adopted and the level of academic performance of pupils?

Methodology

Research Design

This study use the descriptive-correlational research design to find out the extent of challenges encountered, and extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality in relation to performance of pupils.

According to McCombes, (2019) a correlation research design measures a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling the either of them. Furthermore, correlation research design is characterized by a non-casual type of research since neither variable is thought to be leading cause for the escalation of the consequences’ de-escalation.

Respondents

The one hundred twenty-nine (129) out of one hundred ninety-one (191) teachers of the District of La Castellana II, Division of Negros Occidental were the respondents of the study based on their plantilla count and district inventory for permanent and regular teachers.

The District of La Castellana II has a total population of one hundred ninety-one (191) teachers. The researcher utilized a sample survey and stratified random sampling to ascertain the number of respondents. The respondents were chosen through a fishbowl or lottery procedure as the sampling technique in which each name of the participants was written on a piece of paper and placed in a container. The researcher then chose the desired sample size in terms of numbers.

From the total population of 191 teachers who were active in the service as regular/permanent, a sample size of one hundred twenty-nine (129) was drawn using the formula of Slovin with five percent (5%) margin of error and 95% confidence level. After the sample size was taken, the strata or subgroups were calculated using the stratified proportionate sampling technique.

The researcher utilized the stratified random sampling using the one hundred twenty-nine (129) teachers of District of La Castellana II S.Y. 2022-2023 as the respondents of the study. In stratified random sampling, a method of selecting a sample in which researchers first divide a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared characteristics of the members and then randomly select among each stratum to form the final sample (Simkus, 2023).

The following is the distribution of samples using the stratified sampling technique in thirteen (13) schools of the district of La Castellana II namely, Cabadiangan ES, Camandag ES, Don Felix Robles ES, Hiniwa-an ES, Jose Soriano ES, Lalagsan ES, Manghanoy ES, Nato Soliguen ES, Odiong ES, Policena ES, Rosario ES, Talaptap ES, Tipolo-Cabandungga ES.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents by School

<i>School</i>	<i>Population(N)</i>	<i>Sample (n)</i>
A	8	5
B	9	6
C	62	43
D	7	5
E	15	10
F	10	7
G	23	16
H	8	5
I	9	6
J	8	5
K	8	5
L	8	5
M	16	11
Total	191	129

Instrument

This study utilized a researcher-made survey instrument. The parameters used to measure the extent of challenges and strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality in relation to the performance of pupils in the District of La Castellana II, Division of Negros Occidental that undergone a validity and reliability test of the instrument.

The data gathering instrument consisted of four (4) leading parts. Part I contained three (3) items, which were the demographic profile of the respondents. Information on the personal and work-related data of the respondents includes sex, length of service, and civil status. Additional data understood in the profile will be treated as the foundation for the selection of the respondents.

Part II of the survey instrument contained the parts to measure the extent of the challenges adopted by teachers in the face-to-face modality in the following six domains: Answers and responses to each item supported the following scaling: (5) verbal interpretation of very great extent, (4) for great extent, (3) for moderate extent, (2) for low extent, and (1) with verbal interpretation of very low extent.

There are six (6) domains, and all areas have three (3) items to be measured. area one (1) is on parental support; area two (2) behavior management; area three (3) communication; area four (4) administrative work; area five (5) learning styles; and area six (6) educational trends and technology. Part III of the survey instrument measured the extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality, which have five (5) domains, and all have three (3) items to be measured. Area one (1) video-based, area two (2) game-based, area three (3) collaborative learning approach, area four (4) individualized instruction, area five (5) inquiry-based approach.

Part IV of the survey instrument required to answer the academic performance of based on school form 5 or the report on the promotion and level of proficiency of pupils the school year 2022-2023 using DepEd's grading scale.

Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument

In this study, to ensure and establish the validity of the instrument, a survey questionnaire was created by the researcher based on challenges encountered and strategies adopted by the teachers in the face-to-face modality as the basis for enhancement. Adjustments and modifications were made based on the purpose and goal of the study. The research instrument was validated and scrutinized by three validators who were experts in the field of education and doctorate's degree holders. To validate the research instrument, the researcher adapted the criteria developed for the evaluation of the survey questionnaire set forth by Douglas V. Scates and Carter V. Good. The result of the validity test showed "5" with a validity index of "excellent".

Additionally, the reliability of the research instrument was established, it was administered to the selected teachers in the District of La Castellana I. This guaranteed that entries in the questionnaire were correct and reliable. In the case of this study, the questionnaire was given to thirty (30) teachers with the premise that they were public elementary teachers and who were currently teaching and active in the service. The researcher administered the questionnaire once. The data collected, tabulated, computed and scores were correlated using Cronbach's Alpha. The computed alpha which showed "0.963" and interpreted as to "reliable" for the conduct of the study.

Procedure

The researcher followed a procedure in conducting the study. At the beginning of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent (see Appendix C.1), Public Schools District Supervisor (see Appendix C.2) for the approval of this undertaking for the permission to conduct the study in the thirteen (13) schools. Upon approval of the letter, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to one hundred twenty-nine (129) teachers of the District of La Castellana II, Division of Negros Occidental. The researcher visited the school, distributed the researcher-made questionnaires to the respondents, and explained the purpose of the study. The researcher asked the respondents to be honest in answering the survey and assured them that their data were anonymous and kept with utmost confidentiality.

The data gathered from this study were tallied and computed for the interpretation according to the frequency of items checked by and answered by the respondents. Based on the data gathered, the researchers came up with conclusions and recommendations for this research. All data that were collected were concealed with great privacy and confidentiality. The researcher guaranteed that this research is exclusively for academic and educational purposes and reasons only and no other data must be gathered and disclosed. Correspondingly, the researcher treated this research with ethical understanding and significance with professionalism.

Data Analysis

The presentation of different statistical tools was used in accordance to respond to the research questions. After the data collection, the researcher tallied, tabulated, and analyzed the data gathered.

For problem no. 1, which states to determine the teachers' profile in the following areas to age, sex, civil status, frequency, distribution, and percentage.

For problem no. 2, which states, what is the extent of challenges encountered by teachers in face-to-face modality in the following areas: a. parental support, b. behavior management, c. lack of communication, d. administrative work, e. learning styles, f. educational trends and technology, the mean was used.

For problem no. 3, which states, what is the extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality in the following areas: a. video-based, b. game-based, c. collaborative learning approach, d. individualized instruction, e. inquiry-based approach, the mean was used.

For problem no. 4, which states, what is the performance of pupils for the school year 2022-2023, mean score was used. Based on SF

5, or the Report on Promotion and Level of Proficiency of the pupils in the DepEd's grading scale.

For problem no. 5, which states is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered and strategies adopted by teachers, Goodman Kruskal's Gamma was used.

For problem no. 6, which states, is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered and performance of pupils? Goodman Kruskal's Gamma was used.

For problem no. 7, Is there a significant relationship between the strategies adopted by teachers and the performance of pupils? Goodman Kruskal's Gamma was used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyses, and interprets the data gathered using appropriate statistical tools.

Profile of the Respondents

The table below presents the data on the profile of the teachers in terms of their sex, length of service, and civil status.

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Groupings</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex	Male	17	13.18
	Female	112	86.82
	Total	129	100.00
Length of Service	1-3 years	24	18.60
	4-10 years	41	31.78
	More than 10 years	64	49.61
	Total	129	100.00
Civil Status	Single	39	30.23
	Married	88	68.22
	Widow	2	1.55
	Total	129	100.00

Table 2 shows the respondents' profiles according to sex, 17 teachers are male, with a percentage of 13.18 percent, and for female teachers, 112 or 86.82 percent. Findings reveal that the population of female respondents is dominant. In terms of length of service, 24 teachers, or 18.60 percent, have 1–3 years of experience; 41 teachers, or 31.78 percent, have 4–10 years of experience; and for teachers with more than 10 years of service, 64, or 49.61 percent. Majority of the teachers are in 4-10 years in service. For civil status, 39 teachers are single with 30.23 percent, 88 teachers are married with 68.22 percent, and 2 teachers were widows with 1.55 percent. Table showed that majority of the respondents were married.

The Extent of Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality

Table 3 presents the extent of challenges encountered by teachers in face-to-face modality in terms of 6 areas.

Table 3. Extent of Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality

<i>Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Parental Support	3.85	Great Extent
Behavior Management	4.15	Great Extent
Lack of Communication	3.83	Great Extent
Administrative Work	3.92	Great Extent
Learning Styles	4.19	Great Extent
Educational Trends and Technology	4.20	Great Extent
As a Whole	4.02	Great Extent

The table 3 shows the challenges encountered by the teachers in face-to-face modality: parental support has a mean of 3.85 lack of effective communication has a mean of 3.83; too much administrative work has a mean of 3.92; balancing different learning styles has a mean of 4.19; and educational trends and technology which have the higher result with a mean of 4.20. These are interpreted to as great extent. As a whole, the extent of challenges encountered by teachers in face-to-face modality has a mean of 4.02, with an interpretation of great extent. This implies that teachers find it hard during the face-to-face modality especially on using different platforms and utilizing digital technology in teaching, and the challenges they encountered have high results in the different areas. They face different challenges and concerns in the implementation of face-to-face classes through modular distance learning, which lasted for almost two years. Backed by Hodges et al. (2020), it is necessary to investigate instructors' professional development for online teaching, problems related to distance learning programs, and quality assurance to guarantee that remote learning is successful. It is

clear to us that the pandemic would have been a much worse catastrophe for the students without the teachers' effort and tenacity. The COVID-19 pandemic has called into question academic notions of when, where, and how to give education, the value of lifelong learning, and the necessity of learning agility and resilience in times of crisis.

Extent of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality

Table 4 presents the extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality in 5 areas.

Table 4. *Extent of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality*

<i>Strategies Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Video-based	4.06	Great Extent
Game-based	4.00	Great Extent
Collaborative Learning Approach	4.14	Great Extent
Individualized Instruction	4.23	Very Great Extent
Inquiry-Based Approach	4.21	Very Great Extent
As a Whole	4.13	Great Extent

Table 4 exhibits the strategies adopted by teachers in the face-to-face modality. The video-based approach has a mean of 4.06 and interpreted as great extent, the game-based approach has a mean of 4.00 and interpreted as great extent, and the collaborative learning approach has a mean of 4.14 also interpreted as great extent. In individualized instruction which has the highest result and the frequently strategy adapted by teachers, has a mean of 4.23 and interpreted as very great extent followed by inquiry-based approach which has a mean of 4.21 and is interpreted to a very great extent. As a whole, the extent of strategies adapted by teachers in face-to-face modality has a mean of 4.13, with an interpretation of great extent. These implies that the strategies adapted by teachers in the face-to-face modality are effective and show high results. Thus, despite the transition faced, teachers are ready and flexible for the changes in the department and have adapted and implemented them to provide learners with the opportunity to continue to learn and study. In the study of Bassok et al., (2021), some examined several alternative teaching methods, such as having in-person or group sessions with the kids and giving them tangible items to use at home. Suggesting providing more interactive and quality instruction. Alan (2021) supported this claim and urged that such instruction should not only make the interaction between teacher and children possible but also make it easier for teachers to communicate with parents and to plan it with them.

Level of Academic Performance of Pupils

Table 5 on the next page presents the level of performance of pupils in face-to-face modality.

Table 5. *Level of Academic Performance of Pupils*

<i>Level of Academic Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	19		
Very Satisfactory	49		
Satisfactory	54	85.7	Very Satisfactory
Fairly Satisfactory	7		
Did not meet expectation	0		
Total	129		

Table 5 presents the level of academic performance of pupils based on the school form (SF) 5, or the Report on the Promotion and Level of Proficiency. There were 19 classes with outstanding performance, 49 classes were rated with very satisfactory, 54 classes with satisfactory rate, 7 classes have a rating of fairly satisfactory, and none with did not meet expectations. As a whole, it has a mean of 85.7, with an interpretation of very satisfactory. This implies that teachers perform their tasks and duties in their academic performance based on the grades of their pupils; most teachers have satisfactory or very satisfactory results. Moreover, teachers are frontliners in education, and they are expected to perform their best to ensure that learning is evident. It goes above and beyond, though bolstered by Gonzalez et al.'s (2020) study, which discovered that students' improved learning strategies and self-control abilities could be the cause of their rise in academic achievement. The findings indicate there is very little correlation between the teachers' tactics for implementing modular distance learning and the academic achievement were corroborated by Lagrio and San Jose (2023).

The Extent of Challenges Encountered and Extent of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality

The relationship between the extent of challenges encountered and the extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality is shown on the table 6 below.

Table shows 30 teachers rated very great extent in both their challenges encountered and strategies they adopted. 11 teachers encountered challenges with very great extent and with great extent in strategies adopted. 6 teachers rated very great extent on the challenges encountered with moderate extent in the strategies adopted. 16 rated great extent in challenges encountered and very great extent on their strategies adopted. 40 teachers answered great extent on the challenges encountered and they were very great extent on

the strategies they adopted. Only 4 rated very great extent on the challenges encountered and in moderate extent on the strategies adopted. On moderate extent of challenges encountered, 3 answered with very great extent on the strategies adopted. 6 with moderate extent on challenges encountered with great extent on the strategies adopted. 13 answered both moderate extent on the challenges encountered and strategies adopted. No one rated for both low extent and very low extent on the challenges encountered, and strategies adopted.

Table 6. Relationship Between the Extent of Challenges Encountered and Extent of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality

Level of Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality	Level of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality					Total
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Moderate Extent	Low Extent	Very Low Extent	
Very Great Extent	30	11	6	0	0	47
Great Extent	16	40	4	0	0	60
Moderate Extent	3	6	13	0	0	22
Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	49	57	23	0	0	129

Computed value (G): 52.48

P-Value: <0.001

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table shows 30 teachers rated very great extent in both their challenges encountered and strategies they adopted. 11 teachers encountered challenges with very great extent and with great extent in strategies adopted. 6 teachers rated very great extent on the challenges encountered with moderate extent in the strategies adopted. 16 rated great extent in challenges encountered and very great extent on their strategies adopted. 40 teachers answered great extent on the challenges encountered and they were very great extent on the strategies they adopted. Only 4 rated very great extent on the challenges encountered and in moderate extent on the strategies adopted. On moderate extent of challenges encountered, 3 answered with very great extent on the strategies adopted. 6 with moderate extent on challenges encountered with great extent on the strategies adopted. 13 answered both moderate extent on the challenges encountered and strategies adopted. No one rated for both low extent and very low extent on the challenges encountered, and strategies adopted. After computing the data using Goodman Kruskal's Gamma Coefficient, the F-computed value is 52.48 with a p-value of <0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and this means that there is significant relationship between the extent of challenges encountered and extent of strategies adopted by teachers in face-to-face modality.

This suggests that whatever challenges are faced and encountered, teachers can easily adopt specific and effective learning strategies for the learners to guarantee that learning is evident and meaningful. The changes faced by the teachers in terms of their teaching practices during the pandemic are abrupt. The Filipino teachers who were part of this study revealed that they received adequate support from their respective schools, although problems remained in terms of infrastructure, the teachers' competency, especially in ICT, professional development, handling the students in an online environment, and meeting the goals laid out in the lesson plans and curriculum of the respective subjects that they are teaching. Supported by the study of Bautista et al. (2021), during the pandemic, teachers experienced sudden shifts in their methods of instruction. The Filipino educators who participated in this study reported that their schools provided them with sufficient support, but issues persisted regarding infrastructure, the teachers' proficiency with ICT in particular, professional development, managing the students in an online setting, and achieving the objectives outlined in the lesson plans and curricula of the subjects they teach.

Extent of Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-To-Face Modality And Level of Academic Performance

Table 7 that is shown below presents the relationship between the extent of challenges encountered by teachers and the level of performance of pupils in face-to-face modality.

Table 7. Relationship Between the Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality and Level of Academic Performance

Level of Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet expectation	
Very Great Extent	6	22	15	4	0	47
Great Extent	10	21	28	1	0	60
Moderate Extent	3	6	11	2	0	22
Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	19	49	54	7	0	129

Computed value (G): -0.106

P-Value: 0.397

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 7 shows 47 teachers rated very great extent on the challenges encountered in face-to-face modality and 6 have an outstanding class performance, 22 teachers have very satisfactory, 15 with satisfactory, 4 with fairly satisfactory and none on did not meet expectation. 60 teachers rated great extent on the challenges encountered and 10 has outstanding class academic performance, 21 got very satisfactory rating and 28 got satisfactory and only 1 got fairly satisfactory. 22 teachers rated moderate extent on the challenges adopted and there are 3 teachers has outstanding performance of their pupils, 6 has very satisfactory, 11 with satisfactory and 2 with fairly satisfactory academic performance. No one rated for low and very low extent on the challenges encountered.

After computing the data using Goodman Kruskal’s Gamma Coefficient, the G-computed value is -0.106 with a p-value of 0.397 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, and this means that there is no significant relationship between the extent of challenges encountered and level of academic performance of pupils.

This implies that there is no significant relationship between the extent of challenges encountered by teachers in face-to-face modes and their level of academic performance. This suggests that the challenges faced by teachers do not affect the level of academic performance of the pupils. Thus, teachers are resilient and committed to their work and can easily adjust and adapt to any problems and challenges in their tasks and duties. Supported by Tangil et al.’s work (2022). It turns out that there is no statistical relationship between these two parameters; therefore, the two modalities cannot be supported by the students’ grades alone. Based on their educational background, experts believe it is critical to ascertain whether a student is driven externally or internally. According to Slavin (2019), those who are essentially willing to learn do it because they enjoy learning rather than because they are seeking external rewards.

The Extent of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality and Level of Academic Performance

Table 8 on the next page presents the relationship between the strategies adopted by teachers and the level of academic performance of pupils in face-to-face modality.

Table 8. Relationship Between the Extent of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to Face Modality and Level of Academic Performance

Level of Strategies Adopted by Teachers in Face-to-Face Modality	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet expectation	
Very Great Extent	4	18	23	4	0	49
Great Extent	12	24	20	1	0	57
Moderate Extent	3	7	11	2	0	23
Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	19	49	54	7	0	129

Computed value (G): 0.114
 P-Value: 0.353
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 8 exhibits the relationship between the level of strategies adopted by teachers in the face-to-face modality and the level of academic performance. Total of 4 teachers got an outstanding pupils’ performance, 18 teachers with very satisfactory pupils’ performance, 23 teachers have satisfactory pupils’ performance, 4 got fairly satisfactory pupils’ performance and 0 teachers got did not meet expectation. 57 teachers rated on great extent in strategies adopted, 12 has an outstanding performance, 24 with very satisfactory, 20 have satisfactory and 1 fairly satisfactory rating. On moderate extent 23 teachers rated in the strategies adopted with 3 that has outstanding performance, 7 have very satisfactory, 11 satisfactory and 2 fairly satisfactory performance. And none for low extent and very low extent.

After computing the data using Goodman Kruskal’s Gamma Coefficient, the G-computed value is 0.114 with a P-value of 0.353 which is higher than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, and this means that there is no significant relationship between the extent of challenges encountered and level of academic performance of pupils. This suggests that it does not affect the strategies adopted by the teacher to the academic performance of the pupils. Hence, teachers are more resounding and dedicated to the type of work that they do, which is teaching. It goes above and beyond, though bolstered by Gonzalez et al.’s (2020) study, which discovered that students’ improved learning strategies and self-control abilities could be the cause of their rise in academic achievement. The findings indicate there is very little correlation between the teachers’ tactics for implementing modular distance learning and the academic achievement. Results showed that this is not significant and point to a very slight negative correlation between students’ academic progress and the strategies teachers employ (Lagrio, 2023).

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based from the results and summary of findings of the study.

The profile of the respondents in this study are predominantly female, married and with more than 10 years of teaching experience.

Educational trends and technology are the most challenging teachers encountered in face-to-face modality regardless of their sex, civil

status, and length of service.

The strategies that teachers frequently adopted are individualized instruction and inquiry-based approach.

The academic performance of pupils shows a very satisfactory result which is commendable and expected for the teachers to teach best in face-to-face learning modality despite of the challenges encountered and whatever the strategies they adopted.

The extent of challenges encountered by teachers in the face-to-face modality affect the extent of strategies adopted by teachers.

The extent of challenges encountered by teachers in the face-to-face modality does not affect and influence the level of academic performance of the pupils.

The extent of strategies adopted and by teachers in the face-to-face modality does not alter and affect the level of academic performance of the pupils.

Considering the summary of findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

The Department of Education may ensure that teachers are healthy and in their best form to teach, which means they are holistically ready and prepared every day. Maximize teacher contact time with learners so that learning can be guaranteed and strategies, interventions, remedials, and innovations can be implemented. Prioritizing the well-being of teachers may be promoted for them to focus more on teaching and to teach better without the hindrances of too many administrative tasks and paperwork.

The school, school administrators, parents, and community may work hand in hand for the betterment of the teaching-learning process and help teachers and learners overcome the challenges they faced to address the learning gaps and problems.

The provision of support and assistance to learners according to their needs may amplify and improve their learning, and monitoring and evaluation may be properly practiced and implemented.

School heads may exercise their role as school leaders and administrators to support teachers in terms of planning, implementing, and evaluating. This may be one of the steps in ensuring that all teachers are equipped and armored with competency, skills, and knowledge.

Since majority of the teachers described the extent of the strategies they adopted, it may suggest that an enhancement program may be crafted to innovate existing updates, feedback, and technical assistance may be given to teachers on a regular basis so that they may be able to make modifications and adjustments in terms of pedagogy, technology, and practices.

References

Age. 2023. In Merriam-Webster.com. Retrieved July 3, 2023, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/age>

Alan, U. (2021). Distance Education During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Turkey: Identifying the Needs of Early Childhood Educators. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 49(5), 987–994. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-021-01197-y>

Albritton, M., (2023). Issues in Education | Standard Test, Inequity & Adaptive Learning. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/currentissuesandtrendseducation.html#:~:text=Trends%20in%20education%20are%20considered,not%20currently%20working%20for%20students>.

Anero, J.A., and Tamayo, E.S., (2023). Going Back to Normal: A Phenomenological Study on The Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of Junior High School Teachers In The Full Implementation Of In-Person Classes In The Public Secondary Schools In The Division Of Rizal. *Psych Educ*, 2023, 12: 767-808, Document ID:2023 PEMJ1101, doi:10.5281/zenodo.8274909, ISSN 2822-4353. Retrieved from <https://philarchive.org/archive/ANEGBT>

Bassok, D., Weisner, K., Markowitz, A. J., & Hall, T. (2021). Teaching Young Children during COVID-19: Lessons from Early Educators in Louisiana. *Study of Early Education in Louisiana*. <https://files.elfsightcdn.com/022b8cb9-839c-4bc2-992e-cefccb8e877e/20e038ec-8507-4b59-ad28-cc4a43a197b2.pdf>

Bautista, A.P.J., Bleza, D. G., Buhain, C. B., and Balibrea, D. M., (2021). School Support Received and the Challenges Encountered in Distance Learning Education by Filipino Teachers during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*. Vol. 20, No. 6, pp. 360-385, June 2021. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.6.19>

Challenges. 2023. In Merriam-Webster.com. Retrieved July 3, 2023, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/challenges>

Civil status. 2023. [Civil Status Definition | Law Insider](https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/civil-status) Retrieved July 3, 2023. from <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/civil-status>

Davis, L. N., Gough, M., & Taylor, L. L. (2019) Online teaching: Advantages, obstacles and tools for getting it right. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 19(3), 256-263.

Enhancement. 2023. In dictionary.cambridge.org. Retrieved July 3, 2023, from

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/enhancement>

Fauzi,(2020)Problems_faced_in_distance_education_during_Covid19_Pandemic/356684520

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication>

Gonzalez , T., de la Rubia, M.A., Hinz, K.P. , Comas-Lopez, M. ,Subirats , L., Fort ,S. (2020). Influence of COVID-19 confinement in student’s performance in higher education. PLoS One, 15 (10)(2020), pp. 1-25e0239490

Greene, J. A., Cartiff, B. M., & Duke, R. F. (2018). A meta-analytic review of the relationship between epistemic cognition and academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(8), 1084.

Indeed Career Guide, (2022). Effects of lack of communication (plus tips to improve). Retrieved from<https://uk.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/effects-of-lack-ofcommunication>

Julien, G., Dookwah, R., (2020). Students transition from face-toface to online learning at higher education A case study in Trinidad and Tobago. <https://researchgate.net/publication/343996620>

Krieger N. Genders, sexes, and health: What are the connections—and why does it matter? *International Journal of Epidemiology*. 2023;32(4):652–657.

Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, (2021). Behavior management. Retrieved from <https://www.studocu.com/row/document/kwame-nkrumah-university-of-science-and-technology/business-research-methods/behaviour-management/30565988>

Lagrio, R., and San Jose, L., (2023). Strategies and Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Implementing Modular Distance Learning: Impact on Students' Academic Performance, *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 8(4): 451-459 https://scimatic.org/show_manuscript/1193

Length of service https://www.thefreedictionary.com/length_of_service

Lucero, A. I. (2021). Instructional strategies of teachers and academic performance of intermediate learners in Araling Panlipunan. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 2(3), 336–342.

Sigue-Bisnar, M., (2022). Beyond the Return to Face-to-Face Classes. Retrieved from <https://www.granthornton.com.ph/insights/articles-and-updates/1/from-where-we-sit/beyond-the-return-to-face-to-face-classes/>

Tangil, N. A., Legisan, J. J. A., Gajusta, C. J. N., and Bacata, J. R., (2022). Perceived Effects of Teaching Modalities to the Academic Performance of Teacher Education Students. *Canadian Journal of Educational and Social Studies* Vol. 2(6), 2022, pp. 91-103.

Tasan. R.T., (2021). Teaching Competencies and Pupils’ Performance in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning Modality. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*. Volume IJAMS 1, Issue 1, ISSN: 2782-893X.

Vinikas, I., (2022). Video-based learning strategy. <https://www.loyola.edu/school-education/2021/whatiseducationaltechnology.html#:~:https://news.cornell.edu/stories/2022/03/face-face-interaction-enhances-learning-innovation>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Loradel G. Robles

La Carlota City College – Philippines

Arch. Nelson G. Bedaure, PhD

La Carlota City College – Philippines